

Web Appendix 5: Extended Discussion of Ground Truth in AI-Assisted Peer Review

The analysis of ChatSDG+RR7's performance in comparison to the editor-in-chief was robust and yielded encouraging results. However, the lack of direct input and feedback from the editor-in-chief, who served as the only human reviewer, limits our understanding of the optimal AI-human collaboration. For nearly 50% of the reviews, it remains unclear how, or if, the editor-in-chief utilized the evaluations from ChatSDG+RR7. This raises important questions about the extent to which these reviews influenced the final decisions. Were they the primary source of evaluative data? Were they used merely to confirm the editor-in-chief's judgments? Were they disregarded entirely? To what degree were they referenced for guidance?

Moreover, our study carried an inherent bias, assuming that the editor-in-chief was the ultimate authority and final arbiter on the Honor Roll standards of assessment—the de facto keeper of the ground truth. The editor-in-chief made the final determination on whether a submission met the standards for the Honor Roll, regardless of input from ChatSDG+RR7. While this unchallenged authority provides comfort in maintaining human oversight, it also perpetuates the issue of human bias and limitations. Although the traditional model of an editor-in-chief supported by three blind reviewers was designed to balance individual biases, relying solely on one human decision-maker proved problematic. This issue became evident in the retrospective analysis of previously accepted Honor Roll submissions.

The idea of entrusting AI with critical judgments about human scholarship may seem too significant to delegate exclusively to AI. However, there are numerous domains where AI has already proven superior to humans, such as chess, weather prediction, self-driving cars, and autopilot systems. Although both AI and human peer reviewers will inevitably make mistakes, the error rate for humans in peer reviewing is likely to surpass that of AI, much like the safety records of fully autonomous vehicles compare to human drivers ([REF](#)).

Perhaps the most intriguing and important aspect of AI-human collaboration, still in its early stages of exploration, is the question of how ground truth is determined. This paper highlights that this issue is not only a computational AI problem but, more deeply, an epistemological one. The key insight is that while AI relies on predefined standards to process and evaluate data, the determination of those standards—what is considered "truth"—is shaped by human knowledge, biases, and interpretations.

In computer science, ground truth refers to the accurate and objective data or labels used to train and validate models, where truth is objectively defined. However, this definition is highly context-dependent, as the "truth" is only as reliable as the data provided. From an epistemological standpoint, ground truth extends beyond objective facts. It deals with the nature and limits of knowledge—how we come to know what we consider "true." Ground truth in this context raises questions about the origin of the knowledge used to define truth and whether it is unbiased, universally applicable, or subject to human interpretation and cultural context. It also brings into question whether universality is even necessary.

When applying ground truth in AI-assisted peer review, the overlap between computer science and epistemology becomes clear. AI systems like ChatSDG+RR7 rely on predefined standards (ground truth) to evaluate submissions, yet these standards are shaped by human judgment, values, and biases. This presents an epistemological challenge: the "truth" that AI learns is not purely objective but is constructed from human-determined criteria. In peer review, understanding the limitations of both AI and human evaluators emphasizes the importance of questioning who defines the truth. This synthesis calls for a balance between computational efficiency and epistemological awareness when using AI-assisted peer review techniques like ChatSDG+RR7 in determining responsible research.